

PartArt4OW

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Art, Oceans & Water

PartArt4OW

FSTP Call Documentation

Deliverable 2.4

Deliverable description

Deliverable 2.4 presents all the public documents prepared for the PartArt4OW first open call. FSTP stands for “Financial support to third parties” and it refers to the guidelines, templates and support materials prepared for individuals and consortia interested in submitting a proposal under the first open call of PartArt4OW. The content here presented has been published on the project website in a dedicated [page](#) and in a shorter version on the participants portal of the EC:

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Acronyms

EU	European Union
PAIs	Participatory Art Initiatives
WP	Work Package
PAI	Participatory Art Initiatives

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the public documents prepared for the First Open Call of PartArt4OW as well as the method used for their development.

The public documents here included are the following:

- The Guide for Applicants
- The Frequently Asked Questions (FAQs)
- The Call Announcement.

The **Guide for Applicants** includes all useful information about PartArt4OW, the definition of crucial terms such as Participatory Art Initiatives (PAI), and ocean literacy, the eligibility criteria, the process to be followed for submitting a proposal, the selection process, the financial guidelines and several annexes. The annexes are: (1) first open call challenge, (2) list of eligible countries, (3) application form that third parties will use for presenting their project idea, (4) declaration of honour, (5) financial guidelines, (6) selection criteria and (7) contract templates.

The **FAQs** will be updated on a regular basis to add questions emerging by applicants during the call period: the version included in this deliverable is the one available on the project website on February the 3rd. Updates will be made available on the project website and can be consulted at the following link: <https://partart4ow.eu/the-calls>.

All these documents are publicly available on the project website, in a dedicated [page](#) and will remain available for the whole duration of the call that goes from February the 3rd until April the 3rd. In order to support applicants in using the submission platform (EasyChair) a step-by-step guide on how to use the platform has been developed too and is available on the project website together with all the other documents.

All documents will be revised at the end of the first open call period and will be adapted/improved as needed for the second and third calls.

2. Method

The development of the open call documents was led by T6 Ecosystems, responsible of WP2 (PartArt4O Framework - Open calls) and it is largely based on the documents¹ successfully used in the [IMPETUS project](#) in which T6 is involved. The IMPETUS documents, in turn, were strongly influenced by the work carried out in a previous project, called [ACTION](#), in which T6 was involved too.

Nevertheless, it was important to adapt those documents, designed with and for the citizen science community, to the needs of PartArt4OW. In order to do so T6 proposed a first adaptation of the open call documents and mapped the information gaps to be filled by other partners. The exchanges on the development of the public documents began already at the project kick off meeting, while dedicated co-design sessions were organised to assure that the entire consortium could provide input in the document in an effective way. Beside this, T6 carried out desk research to develop a shared definition of Participatory Art and Ocean literacy: two key terms in the context of the project. The co-design work was especially relevant for the development of those definitions, of the selection criteria and of the first open call challenge.

With reference to the latter, the work started - as stated in the DoA - with the analysis of the objectives of the EU mission "Restore and Ocean and Waters by 2030" and the challenges of the UN Ocean Decade initiative. The draft of the Open Call Challenge was then presented to 7 experts representing a sub-set of the stakeholder mapping carried out by CMMI in WP4. The experts represented the art and creativity domain and the marine science domain, most of them having experience in citizen engagement in art and/or science and at least three of them are carrying out cascading calls or similar initiatives. Originally only one co-design session was planned, but in order to accommodate experts' agendas three sessions were organised between the 13th and the 17th of January. Experts received a draft of the open call challenge together with additional information on the process followed for its development and about PartArt4OW. The feedback and suggestions provided by the experts were very useful in order to finetune the call challenge and positively influenced all other documents too.

¹ Thuermer, G., Passani, A., & Reco, L. (2023). IMPETUS D1.1 Open call documentation 1 (2023). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078362>

2.1 Relationship with other WPs

The Guide for Applicants and the FAQs are the results of a team work at consortium level. These documents, indeed, include the timeline of the negotiation, the starting date and other important dates of the accelerator, the monitoring processes of the accelerator, as well as a list of the activities and outputs PAIs are expected to carry out/deliver. This information is related to the work of WP3 (PartArt4Ocean support and acceleration program), 5 (Impact assessment) and 6 (Communication and dissemination). The co-design of the first Open Call Challenge relied on the stakeholder mapping work carried out in WP4 (Stakeholder engagement and ecosystem building).

3. Documentation for the first Open Call

This section includes the Guide for Applicants, the FAQs and the call announcement.

3.1 PartArt4OW Guide for Applicant

Introduction

This **Guide for Applicants** is designed to support organisations and individuals considering a submission to the PartArt4OW Accelerator Open Calls. It is intended to be the main source of information for the call. Therefore, in case of factual conflicts with other sources of information (such as the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website), the contents of this guide should be deemed authoritative.

This Guide should be carefully read in advance. All applicants must make sure that they are able to comply with all the requirements contained in this **Guide for Applicants** (including the Annexes) if selected for the negotiation phase.

Should you have any outstanding queries regarding the application process after reading this document, please attend one of our webinars, refer to the FAQ on the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website, or contact us via email at opencall@partart4ow.eu.

What is PartArt4OW?

PartArt4OW is a project funded by the European Commission (GA 101157247). The main goals of the project are to:

- Strengthen the emotional connection between society, the ocean and the waters;
- Raise awareness of the environmental challenges affecting the oceans and waters across Europe; and,
- Develop a robust transdisciplinary network to support the protection and restoration of Europe's ocean and inland waters.

PartArt4OW seeks to achieve these goals by directly funding and supporting participatory art initiatives (PAIs).

PartArt4OW is delivered by a consortium which includes prominent research and art institutions and foundations, and communication organisations supported by a wide network of experts that will be able to train and mentor the selected PAIs for maximising their positive impacts.

PartArt4OW focuses on **participatory art and creative processes**, and builds on the belief that participation can bring about a deeper engagement of people with the ocean and waters. This can lead to a **paradigm change** for tightening the relationship between society, the ocean and inland waters, and for supporting their sustainable governance.

What is participatory art for PartArt4OW?

PartArt4OW defines participatory art as a process that emphasises the proactive role and participation of citizens, communities and the society at large in creative, innovative and artistic projects. With this, we mean that citizens are not passive viewers but should actively contribute to the project.

Participatory art changes the perspective on the professional artists that is not seen as the sole maker of a creative project; art is seen as a process that empowers citizens and communities through the reinforcement or building of social bonds. Engaging citizens across different stages of the creative process is critical in creating awareness and promoting societal change for the good of our ocean and water.

PartArt4OW is looking for participatory art initiatives (PAI) which will enable citizens of any social, educational and economic backgrounds, and communities (including marginalised groups and groups at risk of social exclusion), to access, understand and contribute to the scientific and social knowledge produced. This knowledge is expected to be linked to the major challenges faced by the ocean and waters (e.g. unsustainable exploitation of marine resources, pollution of the water system; human-induced climate change altering the physical and biological state of the ocean, river and water basins, etc).

The PartArt4OW team believes that art and creativity can play a crucial role in increasing citizens and communities ocean literacy and in supporting them to take action for the protection of our ocean and water. At the same time, the team values interdisciplinary and intersectionality as crucial elements for the success of the participatory art initiatives.

What is a Participatory Art Initiative (PAI)?

In the context of PartArt4OW, PAIs will be trans/inter-disciplinary, intersectoral and participatory six-month projects supported by PartArt4OW via its Accelerator program.

With the term **trans/inter-disciplinary** we mean that the PAIs team should be composed of people from different backgrounds and expertise, who would be willing to go beyond their disciplinary boundaries and collaborate across disciplines. Considering the overall goal of PartArt4OW, it is strongly recommended to foresee the participation of researchers/experts from the arts and humanities, the social sciences and the marine/water sciences. It is important to acknowledge that within PartArt4OW art is seen as a research practice, a knowledge generation method or a support for the heuristic process as those of other research fields.

With the term **intersectoral** we expect people from different sectors working together and collaborating, for example (but not limited to) researchers, scientists, creatives and artists working with civil society organisations, cultural and creative institutions, public bodies (such as municipalities) and businesses. While individual organisations may apply, we give preference to consortia consisting of organisations from different sectors.

With the term **participatory** we emphasise that stakeholder and community engagement will be a central element of the PAIs. Participatory and creative processes can take many forms and can occur at one or more stages of the PAI's lifetime: from the conception phase; to data collection, elaboration and sharing; to the design and performance of the artistic and creative process. Citizens can be involved also in the communication of PAIs activities and results as well as in related advocacy actions.

The overall goals of the PAIs are to (1) increase ocean literacy; (2) increase awareness on the challenges and pressures faced by the ocean and inland waters and (3) mobilise citizens and stakeholders for the protection and restoration of oceans and inland waters.

What is Ocean Literacy for PartArt4OW?

Ocean literacy is defined, at a very basic level, as the comprehension of how the ocean impacts individuals and how individuals affect the ocean. Ocean-literate people recognize the ecosystem services provided by the ocean, can effectively communicate about the ocean in a meaningful manner and make informed and responsible decisions regarding the ocean and resources².

For the purpose of PartArt4OW, ocean literacy encompasses the elements of knowledge and awareness, emotional attachment, changes in attitudes and behaviour and finally opportunities to put new knowledge into practice through actions and communication efforts (McKinley *et al.* 2023).

What artistic and creative expressions are we looking for?

All artistic and creative expressions are welcomed; more specifically, PAIs are expected to use at least one mode of artistic or creative expression: including but not limited to the following expressions: visual (painting, drawing, printmaking, sculpture, ceramics, photography, video, filmmaking, design, crafts, and architecture), literary (prose, fiction, drama, poetry), performing (dance, drama, music, action art, street art), new media, digital art, fashion design and gaming.

Why Take Part in the PartArt4OW Accelerator?

The PartArt4OW Accelerator offers an unparalleled opportunity for interdisciplinary and intersectoral teams to develop participatory art initiatives (PAIs) targeting oceans and water.

² This definition is inspired by the [Maritime Forum of the European Commission](#).

Selected PAIs will receive up to €50,000 in funding and will participate in a six-month accelerator program which includes mentoring, training, and networking opportunities. During these 6 months, PAIs are expected to **finetune the project/initiative idea, implement it at local level and promote it at a broader level.**

The accelerator provides more than financial aid. It starts with an intensive 3-day online bootcamp, providing learning and exchange opportunities on the PartArt4OW topics. This training will equip participants with the foundational knowledge and skills necessary to maximise their projects' impact. At the same time, the bootcamp will be the starting point for connecting selected participants with the mentors.

Participants will benefit from ongoing online mentoring provided by experts in participatory and creative processes; creative, innovative and artistic expression, and around the conservation and protection of marine and freshwater ecosystems. Additionally, tailored training sessions will address the specific needs of each project, fostering effective collaboration between creatives, artists, scientists, and community members. The emphasis on peer-learning and networking is another key aspect, with dedicated sessions offering opportunities for participants to engage with their peers, share experiences, and build a supportive community.

Promotion and visibility are significant benefits of the program. Projects will be featured on the PartArt4OW website and social media channels, providing valuable exposure. Participants also have the opportunity to present their work at the PartArt4OW Demo Days (see below) and other related events, significantly enhancing visibility and impact.

The **accelerator program** is structured into 3 phases: ideation and conceptualization, implementation, and exhibition.

1. **Ideation and Conceptualization** (1 month): Over a 1-month period, participants engage in 6 online group sessions, each lasting 2-3 hours. These sessions cover key topics such as Inclusivity and Diversity, Data and Ethics, Effective Communication, Scientific Communication, Sustainability, Impact and Art, Science Technology and Society (ASTS) collaboration ensuring alignment with PartArt4OW's primary objectives. In addition to enhancing project knowledge, the sessions promote collaboration with other funded initiatives. This phase will support selected teams in finetuning their project idea and workplan.
2. **Implementation** (4 months): While the team develops and produce their PAI, they will also access the project partners' extensive network, receive personalised mentoring (10 hours), and participate in sessions to enhance artistic, creative and scientific knowledge as well as capabilities for improved citizen participation, ensuring the projects' long-term sustainability and impact.
3. **Exhibition** (1 month): The final phase involves presenting the project results at the PartArt4OW Demo Days in Barcelona in **February 2026**. This is a 2-day event which provides a high-profile platform to showcase work to a broad audience, including key stakeholders (such as scientific communication experts, policy makers, harbour managers, activists, etc), and featuring conferences, workshops, and debates. This phase helps increase the visibility of the PAIs, after execution at the local level.

Beyond the core program, PartArt4OW offers additional activities to enhance PAIs impacts. These include the creation of an ecosystem of relevant stakeholders that will facilitate art-science collaboration in the field of ocean literacy and protection. A unique aspect of the program is the PartArt4OW Sailing Lab materialising in a 11-metre oceanic boat. The Sailing Lab connects creative communities, conducts video interviews with key experts and engaged citizens, and develops photographic/video documentation, enhancing the media impact of the PAIs, facilitating dialogue among different actors involved.

By participating in the PartArt4OW Accelerator, PAIs' teams gain access to substantial financial support, comprehensive mentoring, extensive networking opportunities, and valuable exposure. The program fosters innovation, collaboration, and sustainability in ocean conservation efforts, ensuring participants have the tools and resources needed to make a lasting impact. Successful applicants may also feature as case studies in PartArt4OW research, further enhancing their visibility and influence in the field. This accelerator offers a unique chance to advance engagement with ocean and water through creative and interdisciplinary approaches, by contributing to a sustainable and healthier future for our oceans and waterways.

Who is Eligible to Apply?

To be eligible to apply to the PartArt4OW open call, applicants must fulfil the following criteria:

- All applicants must address the challenge of the Open Call, outlined in **Annex 1**.
- They must propose a project that fits the PartArt4OW definition of participatory art, of ocean literacy and of the PAI.
- Individuals, legal entities, and consortia may apply. For consortia, all applicants must be eligible. They must choose a lead who will submit the application and engage with PartArt4OW on their behalf. The lead is the only entity receiving the total requested budget and is responsible for the expenditure of the funds and the complete realisation of the proposed project.
- Every entity is allowed to participate in only one application, either on its own or as part of a consortium.
- Projects already funded by other international, national, local, or private funds cannot apply for funding for the same activities through PartArt4OW. Applicants must explicitly disclose any existing funding in their application and provide clear evidence that their proposed project activities are distinct and not subject to double funding. This ensures compliance with Horizon Europe financial regulations³, which prohibits the same activity from receiving funding from multiple sources. Projects demonstrating complementarities between PartArt4OW funding and other sources are encouraged, provided they maintain transparency and accountability.
- Applicants must be individuals or organisations established or resident in EU Member States or third countries in Europe that are associated or negotiating an association agreement with Horizon Europe. A list of all eligible countries is available in **Annex 2**.

³ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/990fe2a6-8f52-11ef-a130-01aa75ed71a1>

- All applications must be submitted by the deadline (**3 April 2025, 17:00 CET**) with a valid application form (see [Annex 3](#) and the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website).
- All applications must be submitted with a signed Declaration of Honour (see [Annex 4](#) and the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website).

Please note that entities subject to EU restrictive measures under Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) are not eligible to participate in any capacity.

Conflict of Interest

PartArt4OW has the following conflict of interest policy: immediate family, partners, and members of staff of PartArt4OW consortium members (including subcontractors) are prohibited to apply. Those with financial ties to PartArt4OW should declare their conflict, which will be assessed on a case-by-case basis. To declare a conflict or if you have a prior relationship with PartArt4OW that you feel may constitute a conflict of interest, please email opencall@partart4ow.eu for clarification.

What Kinds of Activities are Supported?

PartArt4OW will provide funding for 6-month projects which must be implemented during the PartArt4OW acceleration program scheduled to take place between **1 September 2025** and **27 February 2026**.

All applications to the grant have to be clearly related to the challenge of the Open Call.

The funding can be spent on salaries, equipment, consumables, travel, subcontracting to other entities, and indirect expenditure in accordance with Horizon Europe financial guidelines (see fn. 2). In your application, you will be asked to describe the staff and resources you plan to mobilise for this amount. You may propose any cost items deemed eligible and relevant for the delivery of your project (see eligible costs in [Annex 5](#). Financial Guidelines).

What Happens with Your Results?

All results and outcomes of your project will remain your property, including associated objects and IP.

The EC and PartArt4OW consortium may use, for its research, communication and dissemination activities, information relating to the PAIs' action, documents such as summaries for publication and public deliverables as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material received from PAIs (including in electronic form). The EC right to use a beneficiary's materials, documents and information includes:

- a) use for its own purposes;
- b) distribution to the public;
- c) editing or redrafting for communication and publicity activities;
- d) translation;
- e) giving access in response to individual requests under Regulation No 1049/2001, without the right to reproduce or exploit;
- f) storage in paper, electronic or other form;
- g) archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules
- h) the right to authorize third parties to act on its behalf or sub-license the modes of use set out in Points (b), (c), (d) and (f) if needed for the communication and publicising activities of the EC.

PAIs shall ensure that all necessary authorizations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the EC does not infringe any rights. Every communication product and report of PAIs is to be uploaded on PartArt4OW community on Zenodo, while a CC-BY (requiring attribution) licence will be used for all project's outputs.

We expect all participants to follow an **open science/source approach**, sharing results and experiences widely with the community. Applicants will have to be clear in their applications about how they will treat the data that will be collected or generated through the project. We will give priority to those applications that have a well-articulated plan, as well as applications that are committed to making their data and results available for reuse. PartArt4OW will provide training, and mentoring support to successful applicants to do so.

In addition, the European Commission may ask you to present your work as part of our public relations and networking events to showcase the benefits of the program.

How is the PartArt4OW Accelerator Call Organised?

Three Calls

PartArt4OW will implement three open accelerator calls. The first open call will open on the **3 of February 2025, at 12:00 CET**.

Topic - challenge

The challenge of the PartArt4OW first Open Call is: “**Engage local communities for protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity**”. This challenge is broad enough to allow proponents to explore different aspects of the human-ocean interaction and select the specific topic that is more relevant for the addressed local community.

Projects can focus on ocean or inland waters or on both at the same time.

We expect projects to be fully sustainable, including the use of sustainable materials, circular solutions and renewable energy.

Please read carefully the Open Call Challenge text in **Annex 1** and be sure to align with it.

Application Process

How Can You Apply?

1. The starting point for your application is the [PartArt4OW website](#). Go to the [Call page](#) and you will find there all the information and the templates you will need.
2. Read this Guide for Applicants as well as the FAQ available on the above mentioned webpage. Sign up or watch one of the recorded webinars.
3. Using the link provided on the call page, go to EasyChair (the platform to be used for submitting your application), create an account and start your application.
4. Make sure to answer all questions and upload all relevant documents in PDF format. These documents are:
 - A short proposal. A copy of the application form is available in [Annex 3](#) and on the PartArt4OW [Call page](#) of the project website.
 - A dated and signed Declaration of Honour. A copy is available in [Annex 4](#) and on the PartArt4OW [Call page](#) of the project website. Please download the Declaration of Honour, add your name and surname, signature and date of signature and then upload as a Pdf on EasyChair.
5. Submit before the deadline on 3 April 2025, 17:00 CET.

All documents should be written in English.

Where Can You Find Support?

PartArt4OW will run two webinars where the open call will be presented and where you will have the opportunity to ask questions. Please refer to the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website for webinar dates and registration as well as recordings of past webinars.

If you have a question for PartArt4OW, please refer to our FAQ document (available on the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website) first. If you cannot find the answer to your question, you can email us at opencall@partart4ow.eu.

Please note that all support is only available in English.

How Does PartArt4OW Select Proposals?

Step 1 – Eligibility Checks

PartArt4OW checks if eligibility criteria are met. Proposals considered not eligible will not proceed to Step 2. The criteria are listed under "[Who is eligible to apply?](#)".

Step 2 – Reviews and Shortlist

Eligible proposals will be evaluated by at least 3 reviewers (one from social sciences, one from the artistic/creative domain and one from ocean science) against the following criteria:

- Idea
- Implementation
- Team and Community
- Impact
- Feasibility

Reviewers will be asked to provide a score on a 3-point scale for each criterion. A detailed list of the criteria is available in **Annex 6**. Consider them when filling in the application form.

Only projects that pass the threshold value on each of the criteria will be considered for the next steps of the evaluation.

Step 3 – Interview

Shortlisted applicants will be invited to a remote interview with an expert panel. The interviews will consist of a short pitch of the project followed by questions. In order to complete the scheduled tasks on time, we will operate on a very tight schedule. We will send invitations to interviews between **13-14 May 2025**, including a date and a time slot for the interview. We will not be able to negotiate interview dates/times and related conditions (i.e. online platform to be used for the interviews) with the applicants and may not answer any queries on the subject. The interviews will take place between **15-29 May 2025**. If the applicant or any of their team members are not able to attend the interview, we will have to reject their application.

Applicants who were not shortlisted will also be informed at this stage.

Step 4 – Decision

After the interviews are concluded, the PartArt4OW consortium will decide which applicants will be accepted into the program. We plan to inform the shortlisted applicants about the final outcome on the 30th May 2025. These decisions will be final and cannot be contested. We will notify both successful and unsuccessful applicants about the outcome of the selection phase. For unsuccessful applicants, we will provide the reasons for their non-selection via email; however, we regret to inform you that we will not be able to address further queries or provide additional clarifications regarding the decision.

What Happens When You Are Selected?

Negotiation Phase

If your application is successful, you will be invited to enter negotiations with PartArt4OW. This is a busy period (**3 June - 29 August 2025**) which should end with a signed contract between you and PartArt4OW. The objective of the negotiation phase is fulfilling the legal requirements between the PartArt4OW consortium and every selected project. For this to happen we will have to complete the following steps:

- Due diligence checks: These checks are performed to understand the status of the applicant. We will check your legal status, ethics requirements, and any other details as requested by the European Commission. Should you fail the due diligence checks, PartArt4OW reserves the right to reject the application. As far as ethics requirements are concerned, your proposal will be revised by our Ethical Advisor (according to the RRI principles). Be ready to implement the suggested revisions.
- Project plan and budget agreement: Before starting the Accelerator, the applicant and PartArt4OW agree on project activities and deadlines and assure that the eventual comments provided by reviewers and PartArt4OW partners to the project proposal have been addressed appropriately. We will also assess the costs associated with your project to ensure they are eligible. You will be assigned a person as the main contact point and he/she will go through this process with you and answer any questions.
- If the previous steps are successfully fulfilled, you will be asked to sign a contract with La Sapienza university, coordinator of PartArt4OW, which acts on behalf of the PartArt4OW consortium.

Negotiations will start on **3 June 2025** and must finish by **29 August 2025** with a signed contract. (Please see [Annex 4](#): Declaration of Honour and [Annex 7](#): Contract template). More details and guidance will be provided to successful applicants in due time.

The PartArt4OW Accelerator

Applicants who reach this stage of the process are formally accepted into the 6-month accelerator between **1 September 2025 - 27 February 2026**.

The PartArt4OW accelerator will provide all successful projects with resources, training and mentoring tailored to their individual needs as outlined in the "[Why take part](#)" section.

Funds will be transferred as a lump sum in two stages – 50% at the beginning (first month) and 50% at the end of the 6 month accelerator period (after the final report, in the month following the end of the relevant Accelerator). To qualify for the funding in totality, participants must complete all the activities outlined below.

- Implement a 6-month project as agreed during the negotiation phase and better specified in the work plan that each PAI will develop in the first month of the Accelerator
- During the project implementation:
 - Participate to at least at 4 out of 6 training sessions that will be delivered in the online bootcamp in **September 2025**
 - Attend monthly online sessions with the PartArt4OW mentors to review the project and adjust plans if necessary
 - Participation and provision of required information, materials and proofs during the mid-term monitoring interviews
 - Provide to the PartArt4OW dissemination manager at least 2 blog posts, 5 social media posts, and regular updates about the progress of your project to be published on the [PartArt4OW website](#) and the PartArt4OW social media profiles (both the website and the social media profiles are managed by the PartArt4OW team).
 - Ensure high visibility of the funded projects by actively promoting their results, including showcasing them on the dedicated Mission website "[Restore our Ocean and Waters](#)".
 - Dissemination of project results is essential, and applicants are expected to include a dissemination campaign as part of their project. These campaigns should feature promotional actions that emphasize the role of artists and the creative sector in contributing to the achievement of the Mission objectives.
 - Participate in the PartArt4OW Demo Days which will take place in Barcelona in **February 2026** by presenting or replicating all or part of your main artistic/creative outputs
 - Develop and provide video/photographic material that shows the development of your project during the various stages, including brief video interviews to the artists/creatives and key figures. This material, to be sent to PartArt4OW, will be used as part of the SailingLab activities (e.g. videos, video interviews, artworks, etc.) and final documentation. The video material must be provided on 16/9 horizontal screen ratio, 1920x1080HD or 4k, 25p, encoded in h.264 (quicktime or mp4 container) and delivered via web-upload to PartArt4OW. A rough-cut /cleaning output is required. Video and photo can be taken with pro-cameras or high quality phones but must be shot and delivered in a professional way, following the specific guidelines and release forms that will be provided to all selected PAIS. Raw-News will be available to give further instructions on this topic to all participants.
 - Participate to 2 online impact interviews: one in **September 2025** and one in **February 2026**;
 - Inform PartArt4OW of any potential challenges or issues affecting the project.
 - Participate in a mid-term report interview and prepare a final written technical report detailing all the activities performed and showing evidence of the achievement of the prospective results. You will receive further information on the modality of the interview in due time. For the preparation of the written technical report you will be provided with a Template .

Annex 1: Open Call Challenge

Engage local communities for protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity.

As stated in the [Implementation plan](#) of the EU mission “Restore and Ocean and Waters by 2030” *“Life on Earth depends on a healthy hydrosphere to maintain a rich biodiversity and functioning ecosystems that provide oxygen, drinking water and food. Pollution-free waters are critical for the health of both citizens and the planet. For the citizens of Europe and the world, the health of the ocean and waters will shape their very real conditions of life. Healthy ecosystems support the transition to climate-neutrality, as the ocean is one of the planet’s most important carbon sinks and its resources, wind, tides and waves, provide clean energy.”*

In order to reach the ambitious goal of the Mission, the role of citizens and communities is central. Empowering citizens to take action and be active players of the transitions is fundamental. PartArt4OW believes that by combining art, science and citizens' engagement this can be accelerated. It is important to work across disciplinary and sectoral boundaries in order to spread ocean and water literacy at EU level and restore communities' relationship with the ocean and waters.

What We Are Looking For

We are looking for interdisciplinary and intersectoral projects mixing art and creativity, science and participatory practices in innovative ways. PartArt4OW believes that collaborations between the creative and cultural sectors, the scientific community and civic society organisations can lead to stronger projects but this call is also open to individuals.

We are looking for Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs) whose overall goal will be to:

- increase citizens' ocean literacy;
- increase awareness on the challenges and pressures faced by the ocean and inland waters and
- mobilise citizens and stakeholders for the protection and restoration of oceans and inland waters.

For this **first open call**, the specific challenge to be addressed is that of **engaging local communities for protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity**.

This challenge is aligned with the EU Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters, the EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and the European Green Deal. The Mission's targets include: (a) protecting a minimum of 30% of the EU's sea area and integrating ecological corridors, as part of a true Trans-European Nature Network; (b) protecting at least 10% of the EU's sea area; (c) restoring at least 25,000 km of free-flowing rivers and (d) contributing to relevant upcoming marine nature restoration targets, including degraded seabed habitats and coastal ecosystems.

Participants are free to explore the many aspects and threats related to ocean and water ecosystems and biodiversity (biodiversity loss, algae proliferation, alien species just to name a few). PartArt4OW is particularly interested in:

- the *unseen* phenomenon, such as those related to climate change or those that are not-seen just because we are too disconnected from our ocean to see how it is changing.
- the interdependencies between different aspects of the specific challenge (natural, cultural, political, etc) you will work on and the related societal implications.

Projects can focus on ocean or inland waters or on both at the same time.

Priority will be given to projects that engage citizens in different phases of the project (project design, project implementation, project evaluation, communication and advocacy). With reference to the project implementation phase, citizens can be involved in many ways, not only as audience and participants of workshops, laboratories or artistic events but also as co-researchers (citizen scientists) and/or co-artists.

PartArt4OW is committed to making ocean literacy accessible to all, for this reason priority will be given to those projects that are able to involve people belonging to under-represented groups and/or groups at risk of social exclusion and discrimination (refugees, ethnic minorities, the LGBTQI+ community, individuals with disabilities, low income families, etc). Special attention should be given to those far from art and science and with scarce cultural consumption and educational opportunities.

The focus should be on the communities living in close proximity to ocean, water basins and rivers and assure that the proposed project addresses **key societal and environmental challenges** of those communities.

We expect projects to be fully sustainable, including the use of sustainable materials, circular solutions and renewable energy. Proposals, if selected, must commit to a Climate Pact Pledge⁴ and should work towards full decarbonisation or at least carbon neutrality of the project and of all the proposed activities.

How We Select Projects

All projects will be assessed considering the relevance of the project topic and innovativeness, quality of the proposed plan (including considerations on the ethics and data-related aspects of the project), competences of the team and engaged community characteristics, impact, sustainability and feasibility (see the Guide for Applicants, Annex 6, for more information on the selection process and criteria).

What We Offer

⁴ https://climate-pact.europa.eu/about/about-pact_en

Successful applicants will receive funding and support to deliver a 6 month project. Support will include training and expert guidance from a range of experts within and beyond the PartArt4OW consortium, as well as peer-to-peer exchange and networking opportunities.

We offer a maximum lump sum of €50,000 per project. Priority is given to projects that demonstrate interdisciplinary and intersectoral collaboration.

Funds will be disbursed in two stages: 50% at the beginning of the project and the remaining 50% after the final review, upon successful completion of the project and submission of the required deliverables.

Project Implementation

Successful projects will be required to:

- **Attend the online 3-day bootcamp** organised in September 2025
- **Participate in the training sessions** organised by PartArt4OW throughout the accelerator
- **Refine the proposed project** based on the input from the training sessions and from your mentor and finalise the work plan
- **Provide regular monthly updates** on project progress through monthly calls with assigned mentors.
- **Deliver the PAI project activities** at local level based on the principle of participatory art and in line with your project plan.
- **Participate at the mid-term review interviews** by presenting your mid-term achievements to the PartArt4OW team and gather feedback and implement suggestions
- **Submit a final report and give a presentation** to the PartArt4OW team by outlining activities and achievements at a final review meeting
- **Provide the required information and proofs** during midterm and final reviews
- **Assure a wide dissemination of your project results**, following a dissemination and communication campaign which should be an integral part of your project
- **Showcase your project results** on the PartArt4OW website and the dedicated Mission website.
- Commit to the Make Europe Blue campaign and to the Climate Pact Pledge
- **Participate in the PartArt4OW Demo Days** which will take place in Barcelona in **February 2026** by presenting your results and achievements and/or by replicating all or part of your main artistic/creative outputs
- **Develop and provide video/photographic material** that shows the development of your project during the various stages, including brief video interviews to the artists/creatives and key figures, for use as part of the SailingLab activities
- **Participate in two online impact interviews** with PartArt4OW experts: one at the beginning of the project (Sept. 25) and one at the end (Feb. 26). These interviews will be crucial for assessing the impact of your project.
- **Provide requested materials to the PartArt4OW dissemination manager:** at least 2 blog posts, 5 social media posts, or other updates about the progress of your project
- Inform the PartArt4OW consortium of any potential challenges or issues affecting the project.

- Consider that you might be requested to consider reproducing at your own expense in the closest Mediterranean harbour the realised project in Summer 2026 for the Sailing Lab to document it.

Support and Contact

For further information, please refer to our detailed Guide for Applicants and the FAQs on the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website. If you have specific questions, you can contact us at opencall@partart4ow.eu or join one of our webinars.

Further readings

European Commission, Mission Ocean. Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030 implementation plan.

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-09/ocean_and_waters_implementation_plan_for_publication.pdf

United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development <https://oceandecade.org/> and the related challenges <https://oceandecade.org/challenges/>

Annex 2. List of eligible countries

The following countries are considered eligible for the PartArt4OW Open Call and its funding, as per Annex B of the Horizon Europe Guidelines. Please note that entities subject to EU restrictive measures under Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) are not eligible to participate in any capacity even if included in the list here below.

1. Afghanistan
2. Albania
3. Algeria
4. Angola
5. Argentina
6. Armenia
7. Aruba (NL)
8. Austria
9. Azerbaijan
10. Bangladesh
11. Belarus
12. Belgium
13. Belize
14. Benin
15. Bhutan
16. Bolivia
17. Bonaire (NL)
18. Bosnia and Herzegovina
19. Botswana
20. Bulgaria
21. Burkina Faso
22. Burundi
23. Cabo Verde
24. Cambodia
25. Cameroon
26. Central African Republic
27. Chad
28. Colombia
29. Comoros
30. Congo (Democratic Republic)
31. Congo (Republic)
32. Costa Rica
33. Croatia
34. Cuba
35. Curaçao (NL)

36. Cyprus
37. Czechia
38. Côte d'Ivoire
39. Denmark
40. Djibouti
41. Dominica
42. Dominican Republic
43. Ecuador
44. Egypt
45. El Salvador
46. Equatorial Guinea
47. Eritrea
48. Eswatini
49. Estonia
50. Ethiopia
51. Faroe Islands
52. Fiji
53. Finland
54. France
55. French Polynesia (FR)
56. French Southern and Antarctic Territories (FR)
57. Gabon
58. Gambia
59. Georgia
60. Germany
61. Ghana
62. Greece
63. Greenland (DK)
64. Grenada
65. Guatemala
66. Guinea
67. Guinea-Bissau
68. Guyana
69. Haiti
70. Honduras
71. Hungary
72. Iceland
73. Indonesia
74. Iran
75. Iraq
76. Ireland
77. Israel
78. Italy
79. Jamaica
80. Jordan

81. Kazakhstan
82. Kenya
83. Kiribati
84. Korea (Democratic People's Republic)
85. Kosovo
86. Kyrgyz Republic
87. Lao (People's Democratic Republic)
88. Latvia
89. Lebanon
90. Lesotho
91. Liberia
92. Libya
93. Lithuania
94. Luxembourg
95. Madagascar
96. Malawi
97. Malaysia
98. Maldives
99. Mali
100. Malta
101. Marshall Islands
102. Mauritania
103. Mauritius
104. Micronesia (Federated States)
105. Moldova
106. Monaco
107. Mongolia
108. Montenegro
109. Morocco
110. Mozambique
111. Myanmar
112. Namibia
113. Nepal
114. Netherlands
115. New Caledonia (FR)
116. New Zealand
117. Nicaragua
118. Niger
119. Nigeria
120. Niue
121. North Macedonia
122. Norway
123. Pakistan
124. Palau
125. Palestine

126. Papua New Guinea
127. Paraguay
128. Peru
129. Philippines
130. Poland
131. Portugal
132. Romania
133. Rwanda
134. Saba (NL)
135. Samoa
136. São Tomé and Príncipe
137. Senegal
138. Serbia
139. Sierra Leone
140. Sint Eustatius (NL)
141. Sint Maarten (NL)
142. Slovakia
143. Slovenia
144. Solomon Islands
145. Somalia
146. South Africa
147. South Sudan
148. Spain
149. Sri Lanka
150. St. Barthélemy (FR)
151. St. Lucia
152. St. Pierre and Miquelon (FR)
153. St. Vincent and the Grenadines
154. Sudan
155. Suriname
156. Sweden
157. Syrian Arab Republic
158. Tajikistan
159. Tanzania
160. Thailand
161. Timor-Leste
162. Togo
163. Tonga
164. Tunisia
165. Turkey
166. Turkmenistan
167. Tuvalu
168. Uganda
169. Ukraine
170. United Kingdom

171. Uzbekistan
172. Vanuatu
173. Venezuela
174. Vietnam
175. Wallis and Futuna Islands (FR)
176. Yemen
177. Zambia
178. Zimbabwe

These countries are eligible to participate in the PartArt4OW Open Call. Projects must be delivered in these countries, and applicants must be established in these locations. Please ensure your application aligns with the eligibility criteria specified for PartArt4OW.

Annex 3. Application form

Rules and guidelines

Applicants are required to use the template below. The following rules must be respected:

1. The template **cannot** be changed. When submitting, download a copy of this template, **remove this cover page**, and answer the questions.
2. You **may** adjust the title font size if your title is longer than one line.
3. The proposal must have a **maximum length of 5 pages**. You cannot add annexes.
4. **Do not change** the page layout or margins. You can change the size of response cells. The length of the cells in the template is indicative of the length of responses we anticipate; however, you might need a different text distribution across cells. In any case do not exceed the 5 pages limit.
5. **All questions must** be answered. Leave the questions in - do not delete (parts of) the question or resize the questions in the table.
6. The font size should not be changed from **Arial, 11pt, and single spacing**.
7. Links to external documents that answer a question are **not allowed**. External content will not be considered during reviews. Links to your website or to previous work you have carried out are permitted.
8. The budget **must be for the 6-month accelerator period** and must amount **up to €50,000**
9. Visual elements such as **charts, mockups and screenshots** are allowed, but they must remain readable and not exceed the page limit.
10. The proposal must be uploaded on the **online submission platform** as a **PDF**.

To remain fair to all applicants, proposals not respecting any of the above rules may be declared non-eligible and discarded without further review.

Some additional advice you may find useful:

1. *Read the Guide for Applicants and the FAQs before you start.*
2. *Be brief and to the point.*
3. *Use specific examples whenever possible. Use bullet points, graphs, and tables to bring your point across.*
4. *Be bold, but realistic. We want to fund initiatives that matter and that will be delivered.*
5. *All sections are equally important. Spend time considering all of them, and do not be repetitive in your responses.*

Project proposal title

Summary

Describe the core idea of your project in one sentence.

Provide a brief overview of your proposed project, its main objectives, the specific environmental and/or social challenge it addresses and explain why it can be identified as a Participatory Art Initiative

1. Idea

How does your project relate to the PartArt4OW call challenge?

How does your project promote ocean literacy?

<p>Which are the innovative aspects of your project? <i>(could be related to approaches for promoting ocean and water literacy, could be related to novel artistic and creative expression and many other aspects of your project)</i></p>
<p>Which geographic region will your project cover? Which ocean or water basin will you focus on? <i>Be specific: note oceans, countries, regions, coastal regions, rivers, water basins, town, etc. as relevant</i></p>

2. Implementation

<p>What activities do you plan to conduct over the course of the 6-month Accelerator?</p>
--

<i>Which citizens groups or communities do you plan to work with? What would be their role in the project? How will you attract and maintain engagement from citizens and other stakeholders? Why will people want to contribute?</i>			
<i>What ethical challenges does your project pose, and how will you address them? Do you rely on personal data? If so, how will you manage and store it?</i>			
<i>What are the main results and outputs of your project? Will they be available to others following the principles of Open Science? How?</i>			
<i>How will you use the budget?</i>			
Budget category	Cost over 6 months	Overheads (25%)	Total in Euro
Personnel			
Travel			
Equipment			
Other goods and services			
Subcontracting		n/a	
Grand total in Euro			
<i>Briefly explain the main cost items. Describe the task(s) subcontracted, if any.</i>			

3. Team & Community

Who are the core members of your team? What are their relevant skills and experience? Please mention previous related experiences and artistic works. What are the roles of the members of your team?

***How is or will your project team be inclusive and diverse?
How will your project engage and/or benefit underrepresented groups in Europe?***

4. Impact

***What are the end-benefits of your project, and how will you achieve them?
How will things be different at the end of the six months, in a year, or five?
(please consider social, economic, political, scientific and environmental impacts)***

<p><i>What positive changes do you expect for your stakeholders, including the engaged citizens/communities, by the end of the project?</i> <i>Please mention specific stakeholder groups (such as citizens, researchers, decision-makers, etc.).</i></p>
<p><i>How many people do you plan to involve directly in the project activities and how many via communication activities? Please briefly describe your communication plan/activities including the communication campaign you will carry out.</i></p>
<p><i>How will you assure that your project activities are fully sustainable from an environmental point of view?</i></p>

How will you ensure the work and outcomes can continue beyond the end of the funding?
Indicate any additional sources of funding/support you may need to sustain your project after the end of the PartArt4OW funding and how you plan to secure it.

Empty response box for providing details on funding sustainability.

Annex 4. Declaration of Honour

1. I declare that:

- a. the organisation that I represent is not bankrupt or being wound up, is not having its affairs administered by the courts, has not entered into an arrangement with creditors, has not suspended business activities, is not the subject of proceedings concerning those matters, nor is in any analogous situation arising from a similar procedure provided for in national legislation or regulations;
- b. neither the organisation that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been convicted of an offence concerning their professional conduct by a judgment which has the force of res judicata;
- c. neither the organisation that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been guilty of grave professional misconduct proven by any means which the contracting authority can justify including by decisions of the European Investment Bank and international organisations;
- d. the organisation that I represent is in compliance with its obligations relating to the payment of social security contributions or the payment of taxes in accordance with the legal provisions of the country in which it is established or with those of the country of the contracting authority or those of the country where the contract is to be performed;
- e. neither the organisation that I represent nor persons having powers of representation, decision making or control over it have been the subject of a judgment which has the force of res judicata for fraud, corruption, involvement in a criminal organisation or any other illegal activity, where such illegal activity is detrimental to the Union's financial interests;
- f. the organisation that I represent is not subject to an administrative penalty for being guilty of misrepresenting the information required by the contracting authority as a condition of participation in a grant award procedure or another procurement procedure or failing to supply this information, or having been declared to be in serious breach of its obligations under contracts or grants covered by the Union's budget;
- g. the proposed project does not receive funding for the same activities from other sources.

2. I declare that:

- a. I am not subject to a conflict of interest;
- b. I have not made false declarations in supplying the information required as a condition of participation in the PartArt4OW call or did not fail to supply this information;
- c. I am not in one of the situations of exclusion, referred to in the above-mentioned points 1a-f;
- d. I am an individual or organization located within an EU or in an Associated Country, following Horizon Europe funding eligibility rules. I am not, nor do I represent an

entity subject to EU restrictive measures under Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) not eligible to participate as recipients of FSTP;

e. the proposed project will be implemented in the EU or an associated country.

3. I certify that:

- a. I am committed to participate in the project;
- b. the organisation I represent has stable and sufficient sources of funding to maintain activity throughout participation in the project and to provide any counterpart funding necessary;
- c. the organisation has or will have the necessary resources as and when needed to carry out involvement in the project.

4. I declare that I and other representatives of my organisation will:

- a. ensure the quality, integrity and accuracy of research activities and outputs within the scope of the project;
- b. ensure informed consent from all project participants and protect their confidentiality;
- c. take all steps to protect and ensure the confidentiality of all project participants;
- d. take all necessary steps to protect vulnerable groups who may participate within the project (particularly minors and those with a reduced capacity for consent);
- e. actively seek to encourage participation from underrepresented groups;
- f. comply with any and all legal requirements, both within the country or countries in which the project shall operate and at the European level, in particular the European Union General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679;
- g. will take all reasonable steps to ensure project outputs are made openly available and accessible to the widest possible audience, where this does not infringe upon the rights and expectations of project participants or contravene the legal requirements of the territories in which the project shall operate
- h. be committed to key RRI (Responsible Research and Innovation) concerns and to the Climate Pact Pledge and the Make Europe Blue Campaign.

5. I declare that, to the best of my knowledge and belief, I am eligible to apply for the PartArt4OW accelerator call and all the information I provided in the form is true.

Name and Surname	
Signature	
Date	

Annex 5. Financial guidelines

1. Cost Eligibility Concepts and Exceptions

Costs charged to the PartArt4OW project must align with the following general principles:

- **Actually Incurred:** Only real, not estimated or budgeted, expenses are eligible.
- **Incurred During Project Duration:** All costs must fall within the project period (6 months for applicants).
- **Budgeted and Necessary:** Costs must appear in the estimated project budget and be essential for its objectives.
- **Identifiable and Verifiable:** Expenses must be traceable to the beneficiary's accounts with adequate supporting documentation.
- **Legal Compliance:** All costs must align with national laws on taxes, labour, and social security.
- **Financially Responsible:** Costs should reflect sound financial management principles, including economy and efficiency.

Non-Eligible Costs:

- **Deductible VAT:** Any VAT that is recoverable under the national tax system cannot be charged to the project.

All costs, except for purchased equipment (see below), are recovered 100%, and need to include the indirect costs, charged on top of the total direct costs. All costs should be stated inclusive of any irrecoverable VAT.

2. Eligible Costs

Eligible costs can be categorised based on their form of expenditure.

The total requested amount cannot exceed 50.000 euros including all the following eligible costs (when relevant) and including the indirect costs.

Direct costs:

1. **Personnel costs:** Salaries and social contributions based on actual annual costs.
 - a. Employees: Payment based on employment contracts, with daily rates calculated on annual personnel costs divided by 215 working days.
 - b. Natural persons under direct contract: Self-employed individuals directly contracted for the project.
 - c. Seconded persons: Paid for work seconded from third parties as part of an in-kind contribution.
 - d. SME owners and unpaid natural person beneficiaries: Unit costs for these personnel are calculated based on EU guidance.

2. **Subcontracting costs:** Actual payments made for subcontracting essential project work. Subcontracting must be limited and follow competitive market practices. Subcontracts should prioritize value for money or the lowest price available, based on a minimum of three quotes. Subcontracting to affiliates or between project beneficiaries is prohibited.
3. **Purchase costs:**
 - a. Travel and subsistence: Travel expenses aligned with beneficiary practices, covering transport and subsistence.
 - b. Equipment:
 - i. Purchases of equipment, infrastructure or other assets used for the action must be declared as depreciation costs, **calculated on the basis of the costs actually incurred** and written off in accordance with international accounting standards and the beneficiary's usual accounting practices.
 - c. Renting or Leasing: Eligible if the equipment is rented at a rate not exceeding its depreciation cost.
 - d. Other goods, works and services
4. **Internally invoiced goods and services:** goods or services which are provided within the beneficiary's organisation directly for the action and which the beneficiary values on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices.

This cost will not be taken into account for the indirect cost flat-rate.

Indirect costs:

Indirect costs are within the €50 000 limit for implementing the PAI and cover items such as rent, administration, printing, photocopying, amenities etc. Charged at a flat rate of 25% on eligible direct costs, excluding FSTP, subcontracting, and resources provided by third parties not used on the beneficiary's premises.

3. Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) in the PartArt4OW Project

The PartArt4OW project provides Financial Support to Third Parties (FSTP) to selected Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs). These funds support participatory art projects fostering public engagement with ocean and water sustainability, in line with Horizon Europe guidelines. The FSTP will follow strict criteria and processes aligned with the Horizon Europe guidelines to ensure transparency, accountability, and alignment with project objectives.

Financial support is defined as non-repayable assistance to PAIs implementing participatory art initiatives in line with PartArt4OW goals. These funds cover eligible activities directly linked to the project's objectives, such as art projects fostering environmental awareness, stakeholder engagement, and event participation as specified in the Grant Agreement (GA).

Key FSTP Conditions and Requirements

1. **Maximum Support per PAI:** Each PAI may receive up to **€50,000** to cover the costs of activities that fulfil PartArt4OW objectives. This sub-grant will be funded in two payments.

The first one consists of 50% (up to € 25.000/00) of the total lump sum. It is a kickstarting grant and will be released no later than thirty (30) natural days after the Contract signature. The second one consists of the remaining 50% of the total lump sum. It will be paid no later than thirty (30) days after the final written report (to be prepared in the month following the end of the six-months Accelerator Program).

The second payment will be done after verification of the correct implementation of the Third Party's activities envisaged in the present Contract according to selected KPIs (see the Guidelines for Applicant). The verification will be made by PartArt4OW Consortium, based on the intermediate monitoring activities and the final report.

Payments will not be done during August (summer holidays) and December (for administrative reasons concerning the financial statements closing).

2. Recipient Obligations:

- Selected PAIs must comply with PartArt4OW's requirements on conflict of interest, confidentiality, and ethics as outlined in the GA. They must retain supporting documentation (e.g., receipts and records) for all reported costs to facilitate compliance audits for a period of five years after the end of the PartArt4OW project.
- Recipients are also required to grant access to EU bodies such as OLAF and the European Court of Auditors, enabling oversight of fund use and adherence to EU financial regulations.

3. Reporting and Monitoring:

- PAIs must submit progress assessments as described in the Guidelines and a final report detailing project outcomes.
- Recipients will follow a defined reporting schedule to document activities, challenges, and budget alignments, ensuring consistency with the Horizon Europe financial requirements.

Key Financial Considerations

1. Eligible Costs:

- Eligible costs are direct costs incurred by the recipient for implementing the action, in line with the predefined project objectives. They must be necessary for the project's success, verifiable, and documented according to Horizon Europe standards.

4. Supporting Documents to be kept

Personnel Costs:

- Employment contracts or equivalent.
- Payroll records and detailed breakdowns for productive hours.

Subcontracting:

- Invoices and proof of payment.

- Management documentation confirming subcontractor work completion and cost reasonableness.

Consumables and Equipment:

- Invoices, rental contracts, and equipment usage records as applicable.

Travel:

- Transport tickets, boarding passes, hotel bills, mission approval forms, and meeting records.

Overheads:

- Full documentation on overhead cost calculations and supporting breakdowns.

Bank Statements (for the coordinator):

- Related to PartArt4OW project payments and partner distribution.

Annex 6. Selection criteria

The selection criteria are organised in four dimensions: idea, implementation, team and community, impact and feasibility. Each dimension is organised in several sub-dimensions. For the first four dimensions reviewers will assign a value from 1 to 3 to each sub-dimension. With reference to the dimension feasibility the score is binary (0 if the project is not feasible and 1 if it is feasible). Only the projects that will go above the threshold of ALL the dimensions will be considered for the interviews and final selection step. Besides the below-listed criteria PartArt4OW needs to satisfy a diversity criteria too. This does not apply to the single proposal but it will be considered by the PartArt4OW team during the review phase. Indeed, we need to assure that PAIs are distributed across different countries, consider both oceans and inland waters and that different artistic expressions are represented. This might influence the final selection of the shortlisted proposals.

Idea	
Sub-Dimensions	Guiding questions
<i>Relevance to the topic</i>	Is the project aligned with the PartArt definition of Participatory art?
	Is the project aligned with the PartArt definition of ocean literacy?
	Is the project answering appropriately to the Open Call challenge?
<i>Aim of the project and innovativeness</i>	Does the project have clearly defined, ambitious but also achievable goals?
	Will the project contribute to the current environmental and societal challenges?
	Does the project propose an innovative, change-making approach/idea to ocean and water literacy?
	Is the project scientifically grounded, rigorous and aligned with the state of the art of scientific research?
	Does the project propose creative and novel artistic expressions?
Implementation	
	Are the proposed activities described in a clear way? Is the

<i>Planned activities</i>	logic of implementation well structured and complete?
	How strong is the project proposal in terms of interdisciplinarity and intersectorality?
	Considering the engagement activities proposed: how active is the role of citizens?
<i>Ethics</i>	Does the project properly consider the ethical implications of their activities?
	Does the project properly consider data protection and data management?
<i>Open science</i>	Does the project commit to open science principles?
<i>Use of resources</i>	Are the envisaged expenditures adequate for realising the proposed project? Are there any important activities or requirements (such as dissemination) that are not accounted for within the budget?
Team and community	
<i>Team competences</i>	Does the team have experiences in art and creativity, science, engagement practices and communication?
<i>Inclusions and diversity</i>	Does the project actively engage underrepresented groups (LGBTQ+, low-income persons, ethnic minority, refugee, disabled ...), or will these groups clearly benefit from the project?
	Does the project actively pursue gender balance among participants and the engagement of those far from art and science?
Impact	
	Does the project benefit the citizens engaged in it and/or the local communities? Is the number of citizens engaged

<i>Expected impacts</i>	sufficient for generating a visible impact?
	Will the project have a significant and long-lasting impact in the realms of science, society, economy, and/or art? (not necessarily on all of those realms)
	Is the communication and dissemination plan of the project ambitious and feasible?
	Did the project propose a convincing plan to make the project activities fully sustainable? Are they addressing in a convincing way carbon neutrality and renewable energy issues? Is attention provided to circularity?
	Will the project have a positive environmental impact? i.e increase biodiversity, reduce pollution, etc...
<i>Output and financial sustainability</i>	Is there a preliminary plan to sustain the project beyond PartArt4OW funding? Are the project and its outputs maintained beyond the life of the project? Is there a plan for assuring the future of the artistic outputs? Are new sources of funding likely to become available?
<i>Project feasibility</i>	Can the project be achieved at scale, with the resources and team proposed?

Annex 7. Contract template

The contract template is composed of three documents: hereafter presented as Annexes 7a, 7b and 7c. In Annex 7a and 7b PAIs are defined as Third Party, coherently with the EC wording. Annex 7c is a template PAIs will be required to use for data processing consent purposes.

Annex 7a. Contract for Financial Support to Third Party

BETWEEN:

University of Rome “La Sapienza”, with its registered office in Rome, V.A.T. number IT 02133771002, fiscal code 80209930587, represented for signature of this Agreement by Donatella Strangio her capacity as department Director (hereinafter referred to as the “Beneficiary”)

AND

....., with its registered office in, V.A.T. number, fiscal code, represented for signature of this Agreement by in his/her capacity as PAI (Participatory Art Initiatives), hereinafter referred to as the “Third Party”.

- SINCE the Beneficiary signed the contract n. 101157247 with the European Commission for the purpose of implementing the Project entitled PartArt4OW (Participatory Art for Society Engagement with Ocean and Water) funded under the European Union’s HORIZON-MISS-2023-OCEAN-01 Programme, hereinafter referred to as “Grant Agreement”;
- SINCE, complying with Article 9.4 of the Grant Agreement, the Third Party has been awarded funding under the call for proposals published by the Beneficiary on EasyChair and is consequently identified as the recipient of financial support, pursuant to and for the purposes of the applicable European Union law mentioned in Article 2 of the present contract;
- SINCE the Third Party has been retained for funding by a Commission composed also of external evaluators, it is entitled to receive funding according to the terms and conditions set out under this Sub-grant Agreement (hereinafter referred as the “Contract”) and in accordance with the Guide for Applicants of the PartArt4OW first open call.

The Parties agree

on the following terms and conditions, including those in the Annexes, which form an integral part of this Contract which aims at defining the framework of rights and obligations of the Parties for the development of the Project [NAME OF PAI], the preamble above being considered as a substantial part of the Contract.

Article 1 – Interpretation and reference

- 1.1 The present Agreement is linked to the Grant Agreement n. 101157247 with the European Commission for the purpose of implementing the Project entitled PartArt4OW (Participatory Art for Society Engagement with Ocean and Water).
- 1.2 The present Agreement is being stipulated to allow the fulfilment of the obligations of the parties towards the European Commission and towards other Grant Agreement Beneficiaries.
- 1.3 The Third Party declares to be aware of the content of the Grant Agreement and to have received a copy of it.

Article 2 – *Applicable law*

2.1 This Agreement shall comply with the provisions herein, with the *Grant Agreement* n. 1157247 and with the following legal sources:

- a) the call for proposals published by the Beneficiary to which the Third Party has responded;
- b) the European Union law on participation in Cascade Funding Horizon Programs;
- c) the practices of the European Commission, which interpret and applies the provisions in the point above, in particular the last version of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement and its subsequent updates;
- d) the Italian law integrating the aforesaid legal sources.

Article 3 – *Duration of the Agreement*

3.1 This Contract has a duration of 6 months and enters into force on [.....DATE]

Article 4 – *Subject of the relationship*

4.1 The Third Party shall carry out all the activities outlined in the Open Call published by the Beneficiary, and in the revisited abstract sent to the Coordinator at the end of the negotiation phase incorporating the changes required by reviewers and partners.

Article 5 – *Obligations of the Third Party*

5.1 Obligations and responsibilities of the Third Party are defined in detail in the Guide for Applicants. Additionally, the Third Party shall take every necessary precaution to avoid any risk of conflict of interest relating to economic interests, political or national affinities, personal or any other interests liable to influence the impartial and objective performance of the Project. In case a Third Party is involved in a conflict of interest or in a risk of conflict of interest, the beneficiary must immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

5.2 The Third Party specifically commits to

- a) carrying out the activity described in previous Article 4;
- b) taking part in all the activities and obligations envisaged by the Accelerator program as defined in the *Guide for Applicants*.
- c) prepare and deliver to the Beneficiary all the necessary documentation to demonstrate the effective implementation of the activities (see the *Guide for Applicants*).
- d) respecting the general guidelines given by the Beneficiary to implement the Project and to allow the Beneficiary itself to fulfill its reporting and accountability obligations;
- e) keeping confidentiality, even after the expiration of the present Contract, on confidential information the Third Party gets to know, whether concerning the Beneficiary or to other Third Parties;

- f) informing as soon as possible the Beneficiary of all the events concerning the present Contract, especially those which may jeopardize the appropriate implementation of the activity;
- g) submitting, also after the expiration of the present Agreement, to the controls of the European Commission, of the European Court of Auditors, of OLAF, and any other bodies mentioned in Article 25 of the *Grant Agreement*, providing all required documents and information, giving access to its premises and allowing the necessary inspections and verifications;
- h) comply with the obligations outlined in the *Grant Agreement* which are incumbent on the Beneficiary, within the scope of its responsibilities, with particular reference to Articles 6 (Eligible and ineligible costs and contributions), 12 (Conflict of interests), 13 (Confidentiality and security), 14 (Ethics and values), 16 (Intellectual property rights), 17.2 (visibility), 18 (specific rules for carrying out the action), 19 (general information obligations), 20 (Record-keeping), 21 (Reporting), 22 (Payments and Recoveries) and 25 (Check and Reviews);
- i) keeping records and supporting documents (for 5 years maximum after the end of the present Contract) of the activities to prove declared costs (Article 20 of the *Grant Agreement*);
- j) ensure that the resources allocated for the implementation of the PAI activities will also fulfill the obligations under the *Grant Agreement* incumbent on the Beneficiary and the obligations under this Agreement.
- k) sign a Declaration of Honor (Annex 4) to prove that it can bear the costs of implementing the project before the final payment by the beneficiary (see Article 7).
- l) to notice in writing everything which concerns this Contract to the beneficiary's e-mail address. Any change of persons or contact details shall be notified immediately to the Beneficiary.

5.3 The obligations in paragraph 5.1 cannot be transferred.

Article 6 – *Breach of the contractual obligations.*

6.1 In the event the Beneficiary identifies that a Third Party:

- a) breached its obligations under the Contract, including the lack of impartial or objective performance of the Project because of conflicts of interest;
- b) Stopped to carry out the activities object of this Contract and therefore is not able or willing to continue the Project;
- c) Is engaged in a bankruptcy or receivership process.

6.2 The Beneficiary will give a written notice requiring that such a breach be remedied within 30 days. In case remedies do not arrive in time, the Beneficiary may decide to terminate the contract unilaterally. Moreover, in the event the breach of the contractual obligations has been manifestly intentioned or with gross negligence, the Beneficiary may request the Third Party the refund of the payments made to date.

Article 7 – *Obligations of the Beneficiary*

7.1 The Beneficiary commits to complying with the law applicable to the present Contract and in particular:

- a) to provide the Third Party with all the information necessary for the correct implementation of the present contract (see the Guide For Applicants), at the same time maintaining the confidentiality obligation;
- b) to fund the pre-financing payment and the final payment to the Third Party in the modes and for the amount foreseen in Article 8;
- c) to monitor - together with the PartArt4OW Consortium partners - the proper implementation of the Third Party's project by means of various support activities which are detailed in the *Guide for Applicants*.
- d) to provide a suitable template for the final report to the Third Party;
- e) to provide the Third Party the EC form for transferring bank details (Annex 7b and 7c).

7.2 The EC cannot be held liable for any acts or omissions of the Third Party in relation to this Contract. At the same time, the Third Party is responsible for any act or omission that causes damage to the EC in relation to this Contract.

Article 8 – *Reimbursement of the costs*

8.1 The financial support due to the Third Party is a fixed lump sum of up Euro fifty thousand (€ 50.000/00).

8.2 The financial support will be funded in two payments by the Beneficiary. The first one consists of 50% (up to € 25.000/00) of the total lump sum. It is a pre-financing payment and will be released no later than thirty (30) natural days after the Contract signature. The second one consists of the remaining 50% of the total lump sum. It will be paid no later than thirty (30) days after the final written report (to be prepared in the month following the end of the six-months Accelerator).

8.3 The second payment will be done after verification of the correct implementation of the Third Party's activities envisaged in the present Contract according to selected KPIs (see the Guidelines for Applicant). The verification will be made by PartArt4OW Consortium, based on the intermediate monitoring activities and the final report.

8.4 Payments will not be done during August (summer holidays) and December (for administrative reasons concerning the financial statements closing).

8.5 The present Article shall be applied in a way which ensures applicability also of Article 8.

Article 9 – *Liability of the Third Party*

9.1 The Third Party is liable for any damage caused to the Beneficiary by the personnel resources it provides. In particular, the Third Party shall be liable if, because of its conduct, the Beneficiary is not able to fulfil, totally or in part, its obligations towards the European Commission as described by the Grant Agreement and the obligations taken towards other Project partners.

9.2 Furthermore, the Third Party will have to hold the Beneficiary harmless from the claims of other parties, among which the Third Party's employees or other auxiliaries.

Article 10 – *Termination of the contract before its end-date*

10.1 In case the Third Party fails to fulfil, or breaches, its obligations, the Beneficiary can terminate the contract, giving at least 15 days advance notice, by registered post with proof of delivery, or certified email, where the Beneficiary declares it wants to exercise the right in the present Article. The present Article shall be applied in a way which ensures applicability also of Article 9.

Article 11 – *Data Protection*

- 11.1 The Parties have the obligation to abide by the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data (Annex 7b and 7c).
- 11.2 The processing of personal data shall be carried out lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner, collected for specified purposes and adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which it is processed. The third party must ask each participant in its activities for data processing authorization through the appropriate form (Annex 7c) and keep it for 5 years.

Article 12 – *Intellectual property*

- 12.1 All outputs of the PAIs in the accelerator remain under their IPR (Intellectual Property Rights) and control, though we will encourage open access or open-source models and require data to be published openly where feasible.

Article 13 – *Force Majeure*

- 13.1 “Force Majeure” shall mean any unforeseeable exceptional situation or event beyond the Parties’ control, which prevents either of them from fulfilling any of their obligations under the Contract, which was not attributable to error or negligence on their part and which proves to be inevitable in spite of exercising all due diligence. Any default of a service, defect in equipment or material or delays in making them available, unless they stem directly from a relevant case of force majeure, as well as labour disputes, strikes or financial difficulties cannot be invoked as force majeure.
- 13.2 The Parties shall take the necessary measures to limit any damage due to force majeure. They shall do their best to resume the implementation of the action as soon as possible.
- 13.3 No Party shall be considered to be in breach of its obligations and tasks if such breach is caused by force majeure. A Party will notify the other Parties of any force majeure without undue delay. In case the Third Party is not able to overcome the consequences of Force Majeure within thirty (30) calendar days after such notification, the beneficiary will decide accordingly including the termination of the Contract.

Article 14 – *Information and communication towards the EC and PartArt4OW Consortium*

- 14.1 The Third Party shall, throughout the duration of the financially supported Project, take appropriate measures to engage with the public and the media about the project and to highlight the financial support of the EC. Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Unless the EC requests otherwise, any publicity, including at a conference or seminar or any type of information or promotional material (brochure, leaflet, poster, presentation etc.), must specify that the project has received

research funding from the EC, in the frame of PartArt4OW Grant and display the both the European and PartArt4OW's emblems according to the official models provided by the Consortium. In particular, the Third Party must include the following text for communication activities: "Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them". When displayed in association with a logo, the European emblem should be given appropriate prominence. This obligation to use the European emblem in respect of projects to which the EC contributes implies no right of exclusive use.

14.2 The EC and PartArt4OW consortium may use, for its communication and dissemination activities, information relating to the Third Party's action, documents notably summaries for publication and public deliverables as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material received from the Third Party (including in electronic form). The EC right to use a beneficiary's materials, documents and information includes:

- a) use for its own purposes (in particular, making them available to persons working for the EC or any other EU institution, body, office or agency or body or institutions in EU Member States; and copying or reproducing them in whole or in part, in unlimited numbers);
- b) distribution to the public (in particular, publication as hard copies and in electronic or digital format, publication on the internet, as a downloadable or non-downloadable file, broadcasting by any channel, public display or presentation, communicating through press information services, or inclusion in widely accessible databases or indexes);
- c) editing or redrafting for communication and publicity activities (including shortening, summarizing, inserting other elements (such as meta-data, legends, other graphic, visual, audio or text elements), extracting parts (e.g. audio or video files), dividing into parts, use in a compilation);
- d) translation;
- e) giving access in response to individual requests under Regulation No 1049/2001, without the right to reproduce or exploit;
- f) storage in paper, electronic or other form;
- g) archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules
- h) the right to authorize third parties to act on its behalf or sub-license the modes of use set out in Points (b), (c), (d) and (f) if needed for the communication and publicising activities of the EC.

14.3 The Third Party shall ensure that all necessary authorizations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the EC does not infringe any rights of third parties (including personnel of the beneficiary). Every communication product and report of the Third Party is to be uploaded on PartArt4OW community on Zenodo, while a CC-BY (requiring attribution) licence will be used for all financially supported project's outputs.

14.4 Upon a duly substantiated request by the beneficiary, the EC may agree to forgo such publicity if disclosure of the information indicated above would risk compromising the Third Party's security, academic or commercial interests.

Article 15 – *Assignment and subcontracting*

15.1 The Third Party shall not assign or transfer in whole or in part any of its rights or obligations under this Agreement.

Article 16 – *Language*

16.1 This Contract is drawn in English, language which shall govern all documents, notices, meetings and processes relative thereto.

Article 17 – *Amendments*

17.1 Amendments or changes to this Contract shall be made in writing and signed by the duly authorized representative of the Parties. Nevertheless, in the event the EC modifies the conditions, the beneficiary will amend the Contract accordingly.

Article 18 – *Settlement of disputes*

18.1 The Parties shall endeavour to settle their disputes amicably.

18.2 All disputes arising out of or in connection with this Contract, which cannot be solved amicably, shall be finally settled by the courts of Rome.

Article 19 – *Consent to Personal Data processing*

19.1 The Third Party hereby authorizes the beneficiary to process, including electronically and telematically, and disclose its personal data, for the purpose of fulfilling its social security, welfare, tax and accounting obligations imposed by law and by the regulations of the European Union referred to in the Article 2.

19.2 The Third Party is entitled to the rights provided for by data protection legislation (General Data Protection Regulation – GDPR, EU 2016/679) it they hereby declares to be aware of.

19.3 The beneficiary commits to processing and disclosing the Third Party's data in accordance with the purposes outlined above (Article 7) and to ensure full compliance with all required security measures (Annex 7c).

Article 20 – *Annexes*

20.1 This Contract consists of this core text, including the premises, and the following Annexes:

- Annex 4: Declaration of Honour.
- Annex 7b: European Commission form for Bank Details.
- Annex 7c: Data processing consent form.

Place

Date

The Beneficiary

The Third Party

Annex 7b. EU Bank Details Form

FINANCIAL IDENTIFICATION

PRIVACY STATEMENT https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/about_the_european_commission/eu_budget/privacy_statement_en.pdf
 By submitting this form, you acknowledge that you have been informed about the processing of your personal data by the European Commission for accounting and contractual purposes.

Please use CAPITAL LETTERS and LATIN CHARACTERS when filling in the form.

BANKING DETAILS ①	
ACCOUNT NAME ②	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
IBAN/ACCOUNT NUMBER ③	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
CURRENCY	<input style="width: 50%;" type="text"/>
BIC/SWIFT CODE	<input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/> BRANCH CODE ④ <input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/>
BANK NAME	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
ADDRESS OF BANK BRANCH	
STREET & NUMBER	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
TOWN/CITY	<input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/> POSTCODE <input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/>
COUNTRY	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
ACCOUNT HOLDER'S DATA AS DECLARED TO THE BANK	
ACCOUNT HOLDER	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
STREET & NUMBER	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
TOWN/CITY	<input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/> POSTCODE <input style="width: 40%;" type="text"/>
COUNTRY	<input style="width: 80%;" type="text"/>
REMARK	<input style="width: 80%; height: 40px;" type="text"/>
BANK STAMP + SIGNATURE OF BANK REPRESENTATIVE ⑤	DATE (Obligatory) <input style="width: 80%; height: 30px;" type="text"/> SIGNATURE OF ACCOUNT HOLDER (Obligatory) <input style="width: 80%; height: 60px;" type="text"/>

- ① Enter the final bank data and not the data of the intermediary bank.
- ② This does not refer to the type of account. The account name is usually the one of the account holder. However, the account holder may have chosen to give a different name to its bank account.
- ③ Fill in the IBAN Code (International Bank Account Number) if it exists in the country where your bank is established
- ④ Only applicable for US (ABA code), for AU/NZ (BSB code) and for CA (Transit code). Does not apply for other countries.
- ⑤ It is preferable to attach a copy of RECENT bank statement. Please note that the bank statement has to confirm all the information listed above under 'ACCOUNT NAME', 'ACCOUNT NUMBER/IBAN' and 'BANK NAME'. With an attached statement, the stamp of the bank and the signature of the bank's representative are not required. The signature of the account-holder and the date are ALWAYS mandatory.

Annex 7c. Data Processing Consent Form

This form concerns the data that funded PAIs will acquire from the participants in their activities. This form is to be held by PAIs' referents for 5 years and should not be sent to the Coordinator. *Texts in italics are indicative of the content of the section and should be rewritten according to PAI's and their participants' requirements.* NOTE: This document should be shared with and signed by anyone you invite to contribute data, as an artist, a citizen scientist, or a participant who engages with your participatory art project in other ways. If you collect different types of data, or engage with different persons or communities, you may need separate documents for each case.

Information sheet template

What this project is about

[Give a brief overview of your project that people new to your project can understand]

What we invite you to do

[Explain what you want your participants to do. Be as detailed as possible and explain things like where they need to go (e.g. your office, a harbour, a lake), what equipment they need (e.g. smartphones, waterproof clothes), and what they should do (e.g. take a photo of plastics)]

What data we are collecting from you

[Include all the data you want them to contribute. This data may include but is not limited to:

- *personal data (name, surname, email address and referring institution, if any);*
- *video or photo showing the image of somebody;*
- *audio recordings including voices, music or else;*
- *drawings;*
- *biological data;*
- *....*

Please remember that release forms must be carried and used at all times in the event of filming children and people in close up or making interviews (not necessary for public figures i.e. politicians). The consent of a person to be filmed must be in writing and signed, you can use the release form model indicated [HERE BELOW](#). Minors cannot be filmed on face unless the release form will be signed by the parents or the legal guardian, in this case the ID's data of the parent must be also fully reported on the form itself]

What we will do with this data

[Explain what you plan to do, how data will be processed, stored, analysed and/or published. For example:

- *we will store, use and publish this data according to the EU GDPR;*

- ...]

Why does this matter

[Explain how doing this will benefit your participants' ocean or water literacy or how it is aligned with their needs. You can explain this together with what you want the participatory art project overall to achieve with this data]

What could go wrong

[Explain to your participants how what you plan to do might cause harm, to themselves, to others, or to their environment. It is important that you think seriously about any risks that might occur (e.g. they could fall off a boat), how to minimise these risks (e.g. you provide safety gear), and what would to do if they happen after all (e.g. contact insurance)].

Personal and Sensitive data

[Explain what data you collect about your participants, what you do with this data, and how they can have this data removed (e.g. by contacting someone in your team. Data such as names, surnames, phone numbers or email addresses are personal data. Information concerning sex life or sexual orientation, racial or ethnic origin, political opinion, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic data, health data or financial information (bank account numbers) are sensitive data].

Consent form template

The undersigned..... , born in date
resident in.....Country.....ID.....

Having read the Privacy Policy pursuant to and for the purposes of art. 13 of EU Regulation no. 2016/679 "General Data Protection Regulation" (so-called GDPR)

Declares

- I have read and understood the information sheet. I have had the opportunity to consider the information and ask questions which have been answered to my satisfaction.
- That I and/or my son and/or the minor under my guardianship volunteer to be a participant/contribute to this participatory art project and understand that I and/or my son and/or the minor under my guardianship can drop out of it at any time.
- That I understand that the project may process my personal information (and/or of my son and/or the minor under my guardianship) for the purposes explained in the information sheet. All information will be handled in accordance with applicable local laws and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- I understand that my data (and/or my son and/or the minor under my guardianship) may be used for the purpose of
- I understand that the non-personal data I (and/or my son and/or the minor under my guardianship) contribute to the project may be published under open science principles.

- To agree to be portrayed/filmed/recorded by the contact person[name of the contact person]..... of the Project[name of the project]..... in date..... with my full and unconditional consent, or in the case of a minor with the consent of the parent or legal guardian.
- That the images/video footage/audio-video recordings for which I have given consent will be provided to PartArt4OW and their partners for promotional and informational purposes related to the project itself.
- That PartArt4OW and its partners can store, modify, edit, distribute on web, television, social and other platforms, the Video Photographic images relating to me and/or that of my child or minor under my legal guardianship.
- That PartArt4OW and its project partners will use the images produced at their own discretion in order to be able to produce, present, promote, transmit, distribute, translate or dub, reproduce and exploit the video material, traceable and recognizable to me and/or my child and/or minor under guardianship.
- Of understanding that the [NAME OF THE PAI] coordinator owns legal responsibility and liability for the use of the data described above and of any other data generated or managed during the project activity. PartArt4OW coordinator, partners and associated partners will not be legally responsible or liable for any breach of GDPR rules and regulations due to [NAME OF THE PAI] non compliance.

I therefore authorize the referents of the PartArt4Ow project to use the name, image and biography of me and/or my son and/or the minor under my guardianship, in the informative programming and for any advertising, informative or promotional activity of the PartArt4OW project in all multimedia formats, throughout the world, for a maximum time of 5 years without time limits, releasing PartArt4OW and its partners from any request for rights, economic and non-economic interests, copyrights, current and future claims, even in the event of disclosure by third parties who have replicated the material produced by or for PartArt4OW.

Date and Place

Signature [NAME OF THE PAI]'s contact person:

In complying with legal requirements by signing this Participants Release Form if over 18 years old, or signing on behalf of a child if I'm the parent or guardian.

Signature of the Participant (if adult):

Signature of the parent of guardian:

3.2 FAQs

General

What is PartArt4OW?

PartArt4OW is a project funded by the European Commission (GA 101157247). The main goals of the project are to:

- Strengthen the emotional connection between society, the ocean and the waters;
- Raise awareness of the environmental challenges affecting the oceans and waters across Europe; and,
- Develop a robust transdisciplinary network to support the protection and restoration of Europe's ocean and inland waters.

PartArt4OW seeks to achieve these goals by directly funding and supporting participatory art initiatives (PAIs).

PartArt4OW is delivered by a consortium which includes prominent research and art institutions and foundations, and communication organisations supported by a wide network of experts that will be able to train and mentor the selected PAIs for maximising their positive impacts.

PartArt4OW focuses on participatory art and creative processes, and builds on the belief that participation can bring about a deeper engagement of people with the ocean and waters. This can lead to a paradigm change for tightening the relationship between society, the ocean and inland waters, and for supporting their sustainable governance.

What is participatory art for PartArt4OW?

PartArt4OW defines participatory art as a process that emphasises the proactive role and participation of citizens, communities and the society at large in creative, innovative and artistic projects. With this, we mean that citizens are not passive viewers but should actively contribute to the project.

Participatory art deemphasizes the role of the professional artist as the sole creator of a creative project while at the same time empowers citizens and communities through the reinforcement or building of social bonds. Engaging citizens across different stages of the creative process is critical in creating awareness and promoting societal change for the good of our ocean and water.

PartArt4OW is looking for participatory art initiatives which will enable citizens of any social, educational and economic backgrounds, and communities (including marginalised groups and groups at risk of social exclusion), to access, understand and contribute to the scientific

and social knowledge produced. This knowledge is expected to be linked to the major challenges faced by the ocean and waters (e.g. unsustainable exploitation of marine resources, pollution of the water system; human-induced climate change altering the physical and biological state of the ocean, river and water basins, etc).

The PartArt4OW team believes that art and creativity can play a crucial role in increasing citizens and communities ocean literacy and in supporting them to take action for the protection of our ocean and water. At the same time, the team values interdisciplinary and intersectionality as crucial elements for the success of the participatory art initiatives.

What is a PAI (Participatory Art Initiative)?

In the context of PartArt4OW, PAIs (Participatory Art Initiative) will be trans/inter-disciplinary, intersectoral and participatory.

With the term **trans/inter-disciplinary** we mean that the PAIs team should be composed of people from different backgrounds and expertise, who would be willing to go beyond their disciplinary boundaries and collaborate across disciplines. Considering the overall goal of PartArt4OW, it is strongly recommended to foresee the participation of researchers/experts from the arts and humanities, the social sciences and the marine/water sciences. It is important to acknowledge that within PartArt4OW art is seen as a research practice, a knowledge generation process as those of other research fields.

With the term **intersectoral** we expect people from different sectors working together and collaborating, for example (but not limited to) researchers, scientists, creatives and artists working with civil society organisations, cultural and creative institutions, public bodies (such as municipalities) and businesses. While individual organisations may apply, we give preference to consortia consisting of organisations from different sectors.

With the term **participatory** we emphasise that stakeholder and community engagement will be a central element of the PAIs. Participatory and creative processes can take many forms and can occur at one or more stages of the PAI's lifetime: from the conception phase; to data collection, elaboration and sharing; to the design and performance of the artistic and creative process. Citizens can be involved also in the communication of PAIs activities and results as well as in related advocacy actions. As said, participation can take many forms including but not limited to co-design and co-creation process, citizen science, action research, community art, etc.

The overall goals of the PAIs are to (1) increase ocean literacy; (2) increase awareness on the challenges and pressures faced by the ocean and inland waters and (3) mobilise citizens and stakeholders for the protection and restoration of oceans and inland waters.

What is Ocean Literacy for PartArt4OW?

Ocean literacy is defined, at a very basic level, as the comprehension of how the ocean impacts individuals and how individuals affect the ocean. Ocean-literate people recognize the ecosystem services provided by the ocean, can effectively communicate about the ocean in a meaningful manner and make informed and responsible decisions regarding the

ocean and resources⁵.

For the purpose of PartArt4OW, ocean literacy encompasses the elements of knowledge and awareness, emotional attachment, changes in attitudes and behaviour and finally opportunities to put new knowledge into practice through actions and communication efforts (McKinley *et al.* 2023).

What artistic and creative expressions are welcomed?

All artistic and creative expressions are welcomed; including but not limited to the following expressions: visual (painting, drawing, printmaking, sculpture, ceramics, photography, video, filmmaking, design, crafts, and architecture), literary (prose, fiction, drama, poetry), performing (dance, drama, music, action art, street art), new media, digital art, fashion design and gaming.

What is the Climate Pact Pledge and how can I participate?

In the Declaration of Honour, the [Climate Pact Pledge](#) is mentioned. PAIs are expected to commit to it. The Climate Pact pledge invites citizens, communities, and organizations to commit to concrete actions to combat climate change and contribute to the EU's climate goals. You can participate by making individual or collective commitments to reduce emissions, promote sustainability, and raise environmental awareness.

What is the purpose of the Make Europe Blue Campaign, and how can I get involved?

In the Declaration of Honour, the [Make Europe Blue Campaign](#) is mentioned. PAIs are expected to contribute to it. The [Make Europe Blue Campaign](#) aims to raise awareness and engage citizens in protecting Europe's oceans and waters through educational actions and local initiatives. You can get involved by organizing events, joining community activities, or sharing awareness messages.

PartArt4OW first open call

What is the call about?

The overall goal of your initiative should be the followings:

- increase citizens' ocean literacy;
- increase awareness on the challenges and pressures faced by the ocean and inland waters
- mobilise citizens and stakeholders for the protection and restoration of oceans and inland waters.

More specifically the first open call is looking for initiatives that engage local communities **for protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity.**

⁵ This definition is inspired by the [Maritime Forum of the European Commission](#).

Please read carefully the Open Call challenge in the Guide of Applicants (Annex 1): your proposal must align with the Open Call Challenge text.

How many calls will you have?

PartArt4OW will have three open calls. The first open call opens on **3 February 2025**. Specific dates for the second and third calls will be announced later. This FAQ document is valid for the first open call only and will be updated continuously.

When does the first open call open?

3 February 2025, 12:00 CT (Brussels time).

When does the first open call close?

3 April 2025, 17:00 CET (Brussels time). Please note that the submission deadline is final. No extensions will be provided. Late submissions will not be accepted.

How much funding is available?

PartArt4OW will award a total of €950.000 across three open calls. In the first open call, €300.000 will be allocated. Each PAI will receive up to €50,000.

How many projects will be funded?

PartArt4OW aims to fund 19 Participatory Art Initiatives (PAIs) projects overall. For this call, 6 PAIs are expected to be funded.

How do I apply?

Follow the instructions available in the Guide for Applicants and on the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website.

Eligibility

Who is eligible?

Individuals, legal entities, and consortia may apply. Eligibility conditions are described in detail in the Guide for Applicants. All applicants must be established in, and the project activities must take place in EU Member States or third countries associated with Horizon Europe (see Annex 2 in the Guide for Applicants for a list of eligible countries). Please note that entities subject to EU restrictive measures under Article 29 of the Treaty on the European Union (TEU) and Article 215 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the EU (TFEU) are not eligible to participate in any capacity.

Can individuals apply to PartArt4OW?

Yes, individuals can apply but will be subject to additional checks before funding is released.

Can consortia apply to PartArt4OW?

Yes. The funding is available to consortia, with one lead partner submitting the application and managing the funds. All consortium partners must meet the eligibility criteria (see the Guide for Applicants).

Should proposals be led by artists, creatives and related organisations?

PartArt4OW welcomes projects led by artists, creatives and related organisations but this is not mandatory. Creative expressions should be central to PAIs but this does not mean that artists and creative people must lead the project. It is up to the proponent teams to define the management structure more appropriate to their initiative. PartArt4OW is looking for interdisciplinary, intersectoral, participative initiatives and this should be reflected in the team composition and expertise.

Can I apply if I am already receiving funds from another program?

The activities planned for PartArt4OW cannot receive double funding. Synergies with other funding sources are encouraged if the grants are used for complementary, not overlapping purposes. This should be explained clearly in the Application Form. As an example, if your organisation has received funds for organising an art festival you can still apply for the PartArt4OW for covering activities that will take place during the festival but that are not covered by the funding for the festivals.

Can I apply if my project is already up and running?

New but also *ongoing* initiatives are welcome as long as they respond to the Open Call challenge and respect the fact that double funding is not permitted. Consequently, PartArt4OW expects the proponents to carry out new work as part of the accelerator, adding new activities and outputs to the original initiative. The fact that the initiative builds on an ongoing project and what will be added to it should be clearly described in the application.

Submission

Does PartArt4OW offer a pre-proposal check?

No, PartArt4OW does not assess applications before submission. General questions about the call can be answered via this FAQ document, the two dedicated webinars PartArt4OW will organise, and by sending an email to opencall@partart4ow.eu. Please refer to the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website for webinar dates and registration as well as recordings of past webinars

Can I submit more than one application for the same call?

No. You can submit and/or participate in only one application, either on your own or as part of a consortium.

Can I submit documents that are not in English?

No, all documents must be in English.

How do I submit my application?

PartArt4OW uses EasyChair as a platform for managing the submissions, the review process and the communication with the applicants. You can access the EasyChair platform from the [Call Page](#) of the PartArt4OW website. On the same page you will find the EasyChair user-guide which will support you step-by-step.

How do I know my submission has gone through?

EasyChair will send an automated confirmation email with a reference number. If you do not receive this email within 3 hours from the time of application, contact the [EasyChair support](#) email or the PartArt4OW support email (opencall@partart4ow.eu). In order to be able to activate the support, the PartArt4OW team strongly encourages you to avoid last minute submissions.

Can I change my application once submitted?

Yes, you can update and resubmit your application but only up to the deadline. Only the last submission will be reviewed.

Do I need to submit a signed copy of the contract?

No, you do not need to submit a signed copy of the contract at the application stage. A contract template is attached to the Guide for Applicants (Annex 7) so that you can preview it and be sure you will be able to sign it if your proposal is selected.

Please read the contract carefully, ensure you understand it and indicate your agreement in principle to the terms while making your application on the submission platform. This does not bind you to the terms of the contract. However, since we have only a limited period of time for negotiations and given that we are unable to substantially edit the terms of the contract, applicants who are unable to agree to the terms at application are unlikely to be able to enter the accelerator.

Responsible Research and Innovation

Who keeps the IP of the outputs you develop?

All results and outcomes of your project will remain your property, including associated objects and IP.

The EC and PartArt4OW consortium may use, for its research, communication and dissemination activities, information relating to the PAIs' action, documents notably summaries for publication and public deliverables as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material received from PAIs (including in electronic form).

The EC right to use a beneficiary's materials, documents and information includes:

- a) use for its own purposes;
- b) distribution to the public;
- c) editing or redrafting for communication and publicity activities;
- d) translation;
- e) giving access in response to individual requests under Regulation No 1049/2001, without the right to reproduce or exploit;
- f) storage in paper, electronic or other form;
- g) archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules
- h) the right to authorize third parties to act on its behalf or sub-license the modes of use set out in Points (b), (c), (d) and (f) if needed for the communication and publicising activities of the EC.

PAIs shall ensure that all necessary authorizations for such publication have been obtained and that the publication of the information by the EC does not infringe any rights. Every communication product and report of PAIs is to be uploaded on PartArt4OW community on Zenodo, while a CC-BY (requiring attribution) licence will be used for all project's outputs.

Do I need to share everything openly?

PartArt4OW expects PAIS to follow an **open science/source approach**, sharing results and experiences widely with the community. Applicants will have to be clear in their applications about how they will treat the data that will be collected or generated through the project. We will give priority to those applications that have a well-articulated plan, as well as applications that are committed to making their data and results available for reuse. PartArt4OW will provide training and mentoring to successful applicants to do so.

What do I need to know about ethics?

Applicants must ensure informed consent and data protection practices for any human participants. Ethical research guidelines must be followed. Please see contract template and related annexes (Data processing consent form - Annex 7c) in the Guide for Applicants.

What do I need to know about data?

The acquisition, storage and management of data must always be done in accordance with the EU-GDPR. Please read carefully the Data processing consent form - Annex 7c of the Guide for Applicants. This document is to be used during the implementation of your project to request consent to process the data of your participants.

Evaluation

How does PartArt4OW select applications?

The selection process and related criteria are included in the Guide for applicants.

How are reviewers selected for the evaluation process?

Reviewers are chosen based on their expertise in relevant fields covering the three main focus areas of the Open call: art, social sciences (participatory processes), and marine sciences. Each proposal is reviewed by at least three experts covering the three focus areas mentioned above; the presence of three reviewers ensures a fair and multidisciplinary evaluation.

When will I know if I am shortlisted?

Between the **13th and the 14th May 2025**. On those dates the PartArt4OW team will send the invitations for the interviews.

What will the interview consist of?

A 5-minute presentation of your proposed project followed by up to 20 minutes of questions. It will focus on your proposal with the aim of getting a more precise understanding of your project.

How many people can participate in the interview?

No limit, as long as participants add to the discussion.

When will the interviews be?

Between the **15th and the 29th of May 2025**.

Will I receive feedback?

Yes, all shortlisted applicants will receive reviewer comments.

Can I reschedule the interview?

No, interview dates cannot be negotiated. If no team member can attend, the application will be rejected.

When will I know if my application is approved for funding?

We plan to send the notifications on the 30th of May 2025.

Can I apply again if my application is not successful?

Yes, you can submit a new application in the next call, but ensure it meets the new challenges and requirements.

Costs, Payments, and Legal

What is the amount of funding available per PAI?

Up to €50,000 per PAI.

What can I spend the funding on?

Please see the Guide for Applicants for more details as well as **Annex 5** with Financial Guidelines.

How are the payments scheduled?

Funds will be transferred as a lump sum in two stages – 50% at the beginning (first month) and 50% at the end of the 6 month accelerator period (after the final report, in the month following the end of the relevant Accelerator). Please consider that this implies that some costs must be advanced by PAIs teams.

What do I have to do to receive the final payment?

To qualify for the funding in totality, participants must complete all the activities outlined below.

- Implement a 6-month project as agreed during the negotiation phase and better specified in the work plan that each PAI will develop in the first month of the Accelerator
- During the project implementation:
 - Participate to at least 4 out of 6 training sessions that will be delivered in the online bootcamp in **September 2025**
 - Attend monthly online sessions with the PartArt4OW mentors to review the project and adjust plans if necessary
 - Provide to the PartArt4OW dissemination manager at least 2 blog posts, 5 social media posts, or other updates about the progress of your project so to

have them displayed on the [PartArt4OW website](#) and on PartArt4OW social media

- Ensure high visibility of the funded projects by actively promoting their results, including showcasing them on the dedicated Mission website “[Restore our Ocean and Waters](#)”.
- Dissemination of project results is essential, and applicants are expected to include a dissemination campaign as part of their project. These campaigns should feature promotional actions that emphasize the role of artists and the creative sector in contributing to the achievement of the Mission objectives.
- Develop and provide video/photographic material that shows the development of your project during the various stages, including brief video interviews to the artists/creatives and key figures. This material, to be sent to PartArt4OW, will be used as part of the SailingLab activities (e.g. videos, video interviews, artworks, etc.) and final documentation. The video material must be provided on 16/9 horizontal screen ratio, 1920x1080HD or 4k, 25p or 50p, encoded in h.264 (quicktime or mp4 container) and delivered via web-upload to PartArt4OW. Video and photo can be taken with pro-cameras or high quality phones but must be shot and delivered following professional guidelines, rough cut /cleaning output is required. Raw-News will be available to give further instructions on this topic to all supported PAIs.
- Participate to 2 online impact interviews: one in **September 2025** and one in **February 2026**;
- Inform PartArt4OW of any potential challenges or issues affecting the project.
- Participate in the PartArt4OW Demo Days which will take place in Barcelona in **February 2026** by presenting or replicating all or part of your main artistic/creative outputs
- Participate in a mid-term report interview and prepare a final written technical report detailing all the activities performed and showing evidence of the achievement of the prospective results. You will receive further information on the modality of the interview in due time. For the preparation of the written technical report you will be provided with a dedicated Template.

Is subcontracting allowed?

Yes, however, subcontracting of core tasks is prohibited to ensure the applicant maintains responsibility for key project outcomes. Key tasks must be carried out by the applicant. The task(s) to be subcontracted and the estimated cost for each subcontract must be set out in the Application Form. Once a PAI is initiated, any subcontracting arrangements must receive prior written approval from the PartArt4OW team. This approval must be obtained before entering into any contractual agreements with subcontractors. Subcontracting without such prior consent is strictly prohibited. Subcontractors must be from a Horizon Europe eligible country. Please check Annex 2 “List of eligible countries” in the Guide for Applicants. Indirect costs do not apply to subcontracting.

The Accelerator

Where will the training take place?

Online via platforms like Microsoft Teams or Zoom. The bootcamp (which includes 6 training sessions) is scheduled for **September 2025**. Specific dates will be announced at a later date.

Should I account for training in my budget?

There are no training fees or travel requirements for training sessions for supported projects. All training sessions will be held online.

Will I need to travel?

Yes.

Please note that funded projects will participate in the PartArt4OW Demo Days which will take place in Barcelona in February 2026 by presenting or replicating all or part of their main artistic/creative outputs. Costs for participating in the Demo Days must be covered by the project. Additionally, PAIs are encouraged to include community engagement and outreach events in their plans and budgets.

How much time will I need to spend on Accelerator activities?

You are required to participate in the training sessions and actively interact with the mentor that will be assigned to your PAI. Please expect high-intensity work periods during project negotiation, the mid-term review, and the final review. Additionally, we recommend expecting 1-2 hours of work on a weekly basis to interact with the PartArt4OW team (information sharing, interviews, communication-related activities, etc.) .

What types of mentoring and training will be provided?

The Accelerator includes tailored mentoring sessions with experts in participatory art, marine science and community engagement. Tailored training sessions will address the specific needs of each project, fostering effective collaboration between creatives, artists, scientists, and community members. The emphasis on peer-learning and networking is another key aspect, with dedicated sessions offering opportunities for participants to engage with their peers, share experiences, and build a supportive community. Training and mentoring are designed to enhance the project's implementation and long-term sustainability. Titles and content of the training sessions will be announced later.

3.3 Call announcement

TEMPLATE for Competitive Calls and H2020 Financial Support to Third Parties

Call title:	PartArt4OW First Call
Full name of the EU funded project:	PartArt4OW - Participatory Art for Society Engagement with Ocean and Water
Project acronym:	PartArt4OW
Grant agreement number:	101157247
Call opening date:	3 February 2025 12:00 CET (Brussels time)
Call deadline:	3 April 2025 17:00 CET (Brussels time)
Expected duration of participation:	Six months
Total EU funding available:	950.000 Euros for the three calls that the PartArt4OW will manage. For the first open call the available budget is of 300.000 Euros. Each financed project can have up to 50.000 Euros.

<p>Submission & evaluation process:</p>	<p>Submission process:</p> <p>Applications will be made in English, online, via the submission platform that is accessible via the PartArt4OW website: https://partart4ow.eu/the-calls[ap1]</p> <p>Applications will consist of a short proposal (5 pages maximum) presenting the idea, the implementation plan, the resources needed, the team submitting the proposal, the communities engaged/beneficiaries of the initiative and the expected impact. Administrative information will be required too, and a declaration of honour must be signed and uploaded in the submission portal by proponents.</p> <p>The proposal should follow the template available on the project website: https://partart4ow.eu/the-calls and in the submission platform.</p> <p>The evaluation process can be divided into the following stages:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Eligibility check: Funding is available to individuals and legal entities established in a country or territory eligible to receive Horizon Europe grants. Each entity is allowed to participate in one application, either on its own or as part of a consortium. For consortia, all applicants must be eligible. Project activities must take place in EU Member States, or third countries associated with Horizon Europe. All applicants must submit, together with a project proposal, a signed Declaration of Honour.2. Proposal review: Each proposal will be assessed by at least three reviewers (one from social sciences, one from the artistic/creative domain and one from ocean science) against five criteria: idea, implementation, team and community, impact and feasibility.
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	<p>3. Interviews: Short-listed candidates will be invited to an online interview with an expert panel. The interviews will consist of a short pitch of the project followed by questions.</p> <p>After the interviews are concluded, the PartArt4OW consortium will decide which applicants will be accepted into the program.</p> <p>See PartArt4OW 'Guide for applicants' accessible via the project website for more detailed info on the evaluation process and the selection criteria: https://partart4ow.eu/the-calls</p>
<p>Further information:</p>	<p>Further information [AN2] is available on the dedicated page of the project website: https://partart4ow.eu/the-calls</p> <p>It is also possible to reach the team responsible for the call by writing to: opencall@partart4ow.eu</p>
<p>Task description:</p>	<p>The PartArt4OW Open Call is intended to support the implementation of participatory art initiatives (PAIs) addressing the following challenge: “Engage local communities for protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity”.</p> <p>PartArt4OW is looking for interdisciplinary and intersectoral projects mixing art, science and participatory practices in innovative ways. PartArt4OW believes that collaborations between the creative and cultural sectors, the scientific community and the civic society organisations can lead to stronger projects, but this call is also open to individuals.</p>

The overall goal of the supported PAI will be to:

- increase citizens' ocean literacy
- increase awareness on the challenges and pressures faced by the ocean and inland waters
- mobilise citizens and stakeholders for the protection and restoration of oceans and inland waters.

For this first open call, the specific challenge to be addressed is that of engaging local communities for protecting and restoring marine and freshwater ecosystems and biodiversity.

Participants are free to explore the many aspects and threats related to ocean and water ecosystems and biodiversity (biodiversity loss, algae proliferation, alien species just to name a few). PartArt4OW is particularly interested in:

- the *unseen* phenomenon, such as those related to climate change or those that are not-seen just because we are too disconnected from our ocean to see how it is changing.
- the interdependencies between different aspects of the specific challenge (natural, cultural, political, etc.) you will work on and the related societal implications.

Projects can focus on ocean or inland waters or on both at the same time.

Priority will be given to projects that engage citizens in different phases of the project and that are able to involve persons belonging to under-represented groups and/or groups at risk of social exclusion and discrimination (refugees, ethnic minorities, the LGBTQI+ community, individuals with disabilities, low-income

	<p>families, etc). Special attention should be given to those far from art and science and with scarce cultural consumption and educational opportunities.</p> <p>The focus should be on the communities living in close proximity to ocean, water basins and rivers and assure that the project proposed addresses key societal and environmental challenges of those communities.</p> <p>Successful applicants will be expected to design, implement, and present the findings of a participatory art project to be implemented over the course of six months. In these six months period they will be actively engaged in the PartArt4OW Accelerator, which provides mentoring, networking opportunities, and training sessions.</p> <p>Selected projects are expected to be fully sustainable, including the use of sustainable materials, circular solutions and renewable energy. Proposals, if selected, must commit to a Climate Pact Pledge leading to full decarbonisation or at least carbon neutrality of the project and of all the proposed activities.</p> <p>For more information on the objectives and actions expected to be implemented please visit the project website at: https://partart4ow.eu/the-calls</p>
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4. Next steps

The First Open Call opened on 3 February 2025 and will close on 3 April 2025. During this period two webinars will be organised in order to provide support to potential applicants. The webinars will also be an occasion for participants to ask questions to the PartArt4OW team. If a new question emerges, the FAQs document will be updated and the new version will be made available via the project website. Besides this, applicants can ask questions also via a dedicated email (opencall@partart4ow.eu): this represents another channel through which the team might receive input for improving or updating the FAQs.

Once the first open call will be closed, all public documents will be revised and a new open call challenge will be developed for the second open call that is scheduled for August 2025.

Not only the documents will be improved as needed for the second call, but also the whole process (open call preparation, management, proposal selection, negotiation activities and onboarding of the selected PAIs for the first accelerator) will be discussed in a dedicated reflexivity workshop (as part of WP5). This will take the form of an online interactive setting, using facilitation techniques, where project partners will discuss what worked well, what can be improved and how. The lessons learned will guide the design and implementation of the second Open Call.

The results of the first Open Call will be reported in D.2.1 Open Call report 1 which is due in October 2025.

5. References

Thuermer, G., Passani, A., & Reco, L. (2023). IMPETUS D1.1 Open call documentation 1 (2023). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10078362>